

Clinico-Demographic Profile and Outcome of Mechanically Ventilated Children in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of a Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Mechanical ventilation (MV) is an essential part of present day pediatric intensive care. In recent years, mechanical ventilation has evolved into a highly specialized practice. It is the highest form of respiratory support for critically ill patients and is a lifesaving intervention to support the cardiorespiratory status, until the underlying disease is cured. The study serves to demonstrate clinical-demographic profile and outcome of children receiving mechanical ventilation. The authors also intended to highlight factors associated with poor outcome in these patients.

Methods: The present cross-sectional observational study was conducted in a tertiary care centre of north India, over a period of 1 year from September 2022 to August 2023. All consecutively admitted children aged 1 month to 18 years, who required mechanical ventilation for greater than 12 hours were enrolled. Baseline demographic and clinical profile of study participants was recorded

Results: Out of total 822 admitted patients in PICU, 60 (7.3%) patients fulfilling eligibility criteria were enrolled. The mean, median age of the study participants was 7.5, 7±6.2 years, with a male to female ratio of 1:1. The most common conditions requiring mechanical ventilation were neurotoxic snake bite (23.33%) followed by community acquired pneumonia (16.67%). The mean duration of ventilation was 6±6.4 days. Eighteen children (30%) had comorbid conditions, of which severe acute malnutrition (SAM) was the most prevalent (15%). The mortality rate was 46.7%. The mortality was higher in presence of shock, ARDS (acute respiratory distress syndrome), MODS (multiorgan organ dysfunction syndrome) and with underlying comorbid conditions.

Keywords: Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), Children, Mechanical Ventilation, Pediatric Intensive Care (PICU).

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Introduction

Mechanical ventilation (MV) is an essential part of present day pediatric intensive care. Mechanical ventilation has evolved into a highly specialized practice in recent years. It is a lifesaving intervention for critically ill patients to support the respiratory status, until the underlying illness is treated. [1] Critically ill children generally have a pathological process that affects more than one system and most children require mechanical ventilation during their ICU stay. It is one of the most common interventions

performed in PICU, with 20% to 64% of children admitted requiring ventilator support. [2]. Importantly, it is not without complications, that include atelectasis, air leak syndromes (pneumothorax, subcutaneous emphysema, pneumomediastinum, and pneumoperitoneum), ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP), accidental extubation, post-extubation stridor, failed extubation, vocal cord paralysis and nasal or perioral tissue damage. [3] The outcome of a patient on mechanical ventilation depends on

factors present during the initiation of ventilation, complications which develop during the course of MV and the associated co-morbidities. [4]

As such, ICU practitioners should have the knowledge of the epidemiology of patients requiring mechanical ventilation and the risk factors for mortality. Very little data is available from developing countries regarding mechanical ventilation. The purpose of this study was to assess the demographic and clinical profile, along with outcome of children receiving mechanical ventilation in a PICU of a tertiary care hospital from a developing country. This can help improve the understanding of patients requiring MV which in turn will help to improve therapeutic strategies and outcome.

Methods

The present cross-sectional observational study was conducted in a tertiary care centre of north India, over a period of 1 year from September 2022 to August 2023. All consecutively admitted children aged 1 month to 18 years, who required mechanical ventilation for greater than 12 hours were enrolled. Trauma related and post-operative patients were excluded. Ethical committee approval (No:IEC/024/2023) and written informed consent was taken from each subject, who were followed till discharge/demise. Data pertaining to demographic profile of the patients was recorded in a proforma. This included symptomatology, presence of comorbidities, initial triage classification, final physiological classification, indication for intubation and ventilation, SpO₂:FiO₂ (Peripheral oxygen saturation : fraction of inspired oxygen) ratio, duration and complications of mechanical ventilation. Data regarding health care associated

infections (HCAI) such as ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP), acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) multiple organ dysfunction (MODS) score, hemodynamic support with fluid bolus and/or inotropes, duration of PICU stay and final outcome. Details about the laboratory workup were also recorded.

SpO₂:FiO₂ ratio was taken in place of PaO₂:FiO₂ ratio.[5]

ARDS was graded as per PALICC (Pediatric Acute Lung Injury Consensus Conference) criteria.[6]

MODS score was calculated as per Goldstein Criteria.[7]

Statistical Analysis: The data was summarized and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Window, version 22.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, N.Y., USA). Both descriptive and analytical statistical procedures were utilized. Descriptive statistics like percentage, mean, median, percentiles and standard deviation were used for the presentation of characteristics of mechanically ventilated patients. Chi square and Pearson's R were used for correlation and a p value less than 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results

Out of total 822 admitted patients in PICU, 60 (7.2%) patients fulfilling the eligibility criteria were enrolled. Mean, median± SD age of the participants was 7.5,7 ± 6.2 years respectively. Most common age group affected was 1 month to 1 year (38%). Male to female ratio was 1:1. Referral rate from other districts was 29 (48.3%).

Detailed demographic profile of the patients is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Detailed demographic profile of the patients.

Demographic profile	n(%)
Chronological age in years (mean, median , SD)	7.5,7± 6.2
Age < 1 year	16(26.7)
1-5 years	11(18.3)
6-9 years	8(13.3)
10-12 years	7(11.7)
13-18 years	18(30%)
Gender	
Male gender	30(50%)
Female gender	30(50%)
Socioeconomic status	
Lower	1(1.7)
Lower upper lower	39(65)
Middle lower middle	18(30)
Upper middle	2(3.3)
Glasgow Coma Scale	
Normal	46(76.7)
Low (less than 8)	14(23.3)
ARDS (SpO₂ /FiO₂)	
ARDS present (S/F ratio >264)	28(46.7)
No ARDS (S/F ratio <264)	32(53.3)

The need for intubation and mechanical ventilation was respiratory failure in 46 (76.7%) patients, low GCS in 13 (21.7%) and low GCS plus refractory shock in 1(1.7%) patient.

As per the OSI (Oxygen saturation index), there was no ARDS in 34(56.7%) patients, mild ARDS in 5

(8.3%), moderate ARDS in 13(21.7%), while 8 (13.3%) patients had severe ARDS.

Neurotoxic snake envenomation was the most common indication for ventilation 14(23.3%), followed by community acquired pneumonia 10(16.7%), while poisoning accounted for 6 (10%) cases. Details are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Etiological causes of ventilation

Diagnosis	n(%)	Diagnosis	n(%)
1.Respiratorysystem:	12(20%)	4.Cardiovascular system	4(6.67%)
Comm. Ac. Pneumonia	10	Acyanotic heart disease	3
Bronchiolitis	1	Cyanotic heart disease	1
CMV Pneumonitis	1		
2.Central nervous system	14(23.3%)	5.Poisoning	6(10%)
Viral meningoencephalitis	3	Organophosphorus	2
Pyogenic meningitis	3	Celphos	2
Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM)	1	Paraquat	1
Neurotuberculosis	2	Benzodiazepine	1
Cerebral palsy	3	6.Gastrointestinal/Liver	3(5%)
GBS	1	Acute liver failure	2
Acute necrotizing encephalopathy of childhood (ANEC)	1	Necrotising enterocolitis	1
3.Envenomation	15(25%)	7.Others	6(10%)
Snakebite	14	B-cell ALL	1
Wasp sting	1	Reye Syndrome	2
		Tropical infection	1
		Familial Glucocorticoid	1
		deficiency	
		Late onset HDN	1

Comorbid conditions were found in 30% of ventilated children. Most common comorbidity was severe acute malnutrition (15%). Details are depicted in Table 3.

Table 3: Associated comorbid conditions.

Co-morbid condition	n(%)
Severe acute malnutrition	9(15)
Congenital heart disease	4(6.7)
Cerebral palsy	3(5)
Down Syndrome	2(3.3)
B-cell ALL	1(1.7)
Familial glucocorticoid deficiency	1(1.7)
Immunodeficiency	1(1.7)

Table 4 depicts the laboratory profile of admitted children. Median hemoglobin, platelet count and serum albumin levels were on the lower side in critically sick patients.

Table 4: Laboratory investigations of the study participants.

S No.	Parameter	Median ± IQR
1	Hemoglobin(gm%)	10.5±3.75
2	Leucocyte count x10 ³	9.55±7.63
3	Platelet count x10 ³	149.5±180.5
4	Urea (mg%)	37±32
5	Creatinine (mg%)	0.69±0.38
6	Aspartate-transaminase (SGOT) IU/L	50.5±121.25
7	Alanine-transaminase (SGPT) IU/L	48±132.7
8	Albumin (gm%)	3.7±1.08

The mean, median ± SD duration of mechanical ventilation in this study was 6, 4±6.4 days respectively with the minimum duration being 12 hours and maximum being 38 days.

In our study, the most common complication was ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) in 10 (16.7%) cases, followed by pneumothorax and lung

collapse in 3 (5%) patients each, while there was 1 (1.7%) case of accidental extubation.

This study shows a statistically significant association of VAP with prolonged duration of

mechanical ventilation with a p value of 0.0007. Table 5 shows the relationship between duration of ventilation and incidence of VAP.

Table 5: Relationship between duration of ventilation and incidence of VAP.

Duration of ventilation	Number ventilated	Incidence of VAP n(%)	P value
7-14days	15	5(33.3)	
15-28 days	4	4(75)	
>28 days	1	1(100)	

The most common organism causing VAP was *Acinetobacter baumannii*, having been isolated in 80% cases, followed by *Klebsiella pneumonia* (5%) and Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (5%).

The mean duration of PICU stay was 8±8 days and the mean duration of hospital stay was 11±10 days.

In our study, 28 mechanically ventilated patients succumbed to their illness, with a mortality rate of 46.7%. The highest mortality was seen in patients with congenital heart disease (75%) followed by central nervous system disease. Details are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Relationship of mortality with underlying cause.

Diagnosis	Mortality rate n(%)
Congenital heart disease	3 (75%)
Central nervous system disease	9 (64.29%)
Poisoning	4 (66.67%)
Gastroenterology/Liver disease	2 (66.67%)
Envenomation	2 (13.33%)

The best outcomes were seen in cases of envenomation. The study participants aged 1 month to 1 year had the highest mortality rate(57.1%) while lowest was among adolescents aged 15-18years (36.4%), but this was not statistically significant (p value 0.872).

There was a significant association between presence of comorbid conditions and mortality . The mortality rate was 66.7% among patients with

comorbidities versus 39% in those without any comorbidity, with a p-value of 0.042. Severe acute malnutrition was the most prevalent comorbidity followed by congenital heart disease.

Also mortality was more when patient had associated complications like shock, ARDS and multiorgan failure dysfunction (MODS).Details are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Relationship of mortality rate with presence of comorbidities/complication.

Co-morbidity/complication	Severity	Mortality (%)	P value
Comorbidity	Present	66.7	0.042
	Absent	39	
Shock	No inotrope	37.5	0.004
	Inotrope needed	83	
ARDS	No	26.5	0.003
	Mild	60	
	Moderate	69.2	
	Severe	87.5	
MODS(Goldstein)	1	No mortality	0.0001
	5-6	100	

In our study, multiorgan dysfunction was gauged on the basis of Goldstein criteria and a low MODS score was associated with better outcomes. A higher MODS score was associated with significantly higher mortality. In our study, the mortality rate was above 90% in patients with a MODS score of 4 and higher.

Discussion

In our study, 60 patients were enrolled during the study period of 1 year with a male to female ratio of 1:1. The mean, median ± SD age of study participants in our study was 7.5, 7±6.2 years with majority of children in the infant age group and 10-14 years age group(23.3% each). In a study by Mukhtar et'al^[8], the mean age was 3 years with most

of the patients falling in the infant bracket. They observed male preponderance (59.6%). Similarly Heye et al^[9], in their study found that the majority of ventilated patients were infants and 63.6% were male. Kendrili et al [10] reported a mean age of 3 years in their study with a majority of patients being under 5 years old (75%). We in our study observed two brackets of age groups for ventilation. The mean age and gender of ventilated patients could be reflective of the general population of children presenting to the emergency department with the younger children presenting with severe disease requiring mechanical ventilation. The reason for adolescent age group could probably be more cases of envenomation requiring ventilation in our area.

Majority of patients requiring ventilation in our study belonged to lower upper lower class (65%). Rocha V et al [11] in their meta-analysis found that children, adolescents and young adults from disadvantaged socioeconomic circumstances had lower respiratory function. The presentation of boys respiratory health inequalities were higher.

Holden KA et al [12] studied the impact of poor housing and indoor air quality on respiratory health in children. They also found that children living in from lower-income backgrounds are most at risk of living in substandard housing posing a serious threat to respiratory health. Similar inverse relationship between socioeconomic and overall health was found by Jiao K et al [13].

This could also be due to ignorance and delayed admission to hospital leading to more severity of disease.

Half (49%) patients were referred from other districts for ventilation. Chances of complications and mortality are more when initial time of management is lost. Lodaria B [14] in his study observed better outcome in terms of mortality if patient comes early.

The most common indication of mechanical ventilation in our study was respiratory failure (76.7%) of which the major cause was neurotoxic snake bite (30.43%) followed by community acquired pneumonia (21.7%). The second most common indication was low GCS (21.7%) secondary to meningoencephalitis (23%). This was also noted in a study by done by Farias et al^[2] in which respiratory failure was the main indication (70%) secondary to pulmonary disease. Bhoori et al [15] reported respiratory failure secondary to CNS/respiratory pathology (22.2%) as the most common indication and Kendrili et al [10] reported respiratory failure (64.8%) secondary to pneumonia (69.5%) as most common cause.

Comorbid conditions were associated with almost one third (30%) of our ventilated patients out of which severe acute malnutrition (SAM) was most

common (15%) followed by congenital heart disease (6.7%). This was contrary to Sahoo et al study [4], in which 67% of the study participants had comorbidities out of which CHD and MODS were the most prevalent. Anitha et al [1] reported that 24% of the study participants had comorbid conditions with cerebral palsy and congenital heart disease being the most common. Heye et al study^[9] had reported that 41.8% of their patients had comorbid conditions with the majority having malignancy (16.8%) followed by CHD (12.2%). These could be reflective of the variation in comorbidities of the children presenting to PICU of the health centers.

In laboratory profile of ventilated patients median hemoglobin, platelet count and serum albumin levels were on the lower side with mild transaminitis. Bekhit OE et al in their study^[16] found that incidence of hypoalbuminemia was 26%. Mortality was more in patients who had hypoalbuminemia at admission.

Complications were present in 17 out of 60 patients in our study (28.4%) with the most common being ventilator associated pneumonia (16.7%). Longer is the duration of ventilation more is the chance of getting VAP. This was also seen in Heye et al. study [9] with 18% patients contracted VAP during ventilation. Mukhtar et al. [8] reported lobar atelectasis as the most common complication (4.6%) which was also reported as 26.3% in Kendrili et al study [10] whereas laryngeal edema (11%) was reported by Bhoori et al [11]. Lodaria B [14] found similar rate of complications in his study (26.39%) but rate of VAP was only 6.94%. This was attributed to less crowding of PICU, aseptic precaution, proper bed ratio, location in rural area favorable healthcare personnel, above all being in rural area leading the patients to reach the hospital directly without visiting other places which might have prevented development of cross infection.

Those who developed VAP mortality rate was of 50% in our study. Similarly, the mortality rate in VAP was 42.4% in a study by Vijay G et al [17] and 28.4% in a study by Mahantesh et al [18]. The variation in mortality can be explained based on the underlying disease for which the participants were initially ventilated, delayed referral, cross infection, load of patients.

In our study organisms causing VAP were *Acinetobacter baumannii*, being the most common organism (80%) followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (5%) and Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (5%). This was similar to the study done by Vijay G et al [17] in which *Acinetobacter* (47%) was the most common organism isolated followed by *Pseudomonas* (28%) and *Klebsiella* (15%). Mahantesh et al [18] also reported in their study that *Acinetobacter* was the most common organism causing VAP (62%) followed by *Pseudomonas* (31%) and

Klebsiella (22.97%) with only one case of Methicillin sensitive Staphylococcus aureus. This reflects the similarities in organisms isolated in different PICU setups. The mean, median duration of mechanical ventilation was 6 ± 6.4 days with a maximum duration of 38 days. In Bhuri et al study [11], the mean duration was 4.2 days, in Heye et al study [9] it was 4.4 days whereas it was 2.1 days in Mukhtar et al study [8]. The reason for the difference in the mean duration of ventilation between various studies and ours could be due to various factors such as inclusion of post-operative patients (not included in our studies) and patients requiring ventilation for reversible/transient causes that resolved within the

first 12 hours of ventilation which was not so in our study as those patients were excluded. and higher incidence of VAP .

The mean duration of PICU stay was 8 ± 8 days hospital stay was 11 ± 10 days, which was similar to Sahoo et al study [4] in which the mean duration of PICU stay was 10 days and hospital stay was 12.6 days.

The mortality rate in our study was 46.7%. There is significant variation in different studies in relation to mortality rate. The mortality rate in various studies is listed below (Table 8):

Table 8: Showing comparison of mortality.

Author	Year	Sample size	Type of study	Mortality rate
Heye et al [9]	2019	202	Cross-sectional	59.1%
Kendrili et al [10]	2006	407	Retrospective	58.3%
Dharmaraj et al [19]	2016	56	Retrospective	55.35%
Our study	2023	60	Prospective	46.7%
Farias et al [2]	2012	1185	Prospective cohort	39%(ARDS)
Bhuri et al [11]	2017	72	Prospective Observational	38.89%
Sahoo et al [4]	2018	101	Retrospective	38.6%
Anitha et al [1]	2016	111	Retrospective	36.9%
Mukhtar et al [8]	2014	307	Retrospective Cohort	30.3%
Benjamin et al [20]	1990	204	Prospective	7 to 10.7%
Randolph et al [21]	2003	1096	Observational	1.6%

In our study, the highest mortality was seen in participants with congenital heart disease (75%) followed by central nervous system pathology (64.3%). In contrast, Heye et al [9] reported renal pathology with highest mortality rate (83%) followed by sepsis (82.3%) and malignancy (75%) whereas Sahoo et al [4] reported the highest mortality rate in participants with respiratory disease followed by neurological illness. This can be explained by the diverse nature of conditions being managed in different PICU setups.

Eighteen patients (30%) who required mechanical ventilation had comorbid conditions and 66.67% of these children did not survive, versus a mortality rate of 39% in those without comorbid conditions which was statistically significant ($p = 0.042$). This was similar to Heye et al study [9] in which the mortality was 60.8% in patients with comorbid conditions. The study done by Sahoo et al [4] described 67% of patients as having comorbid conditions and in Liu et al study [17], comorbid conditions were associated with longer duration of mechanical ventilation.

In our study, mortality rate was highest among infants (57.14%) and the lowest amongst adolescents aged 15-18 years (36.36%). In comparison, Heye et al [9] reported a similar trend of higher mortality in infants (63.9%) as compared to those aged 1-12 years (55%)

There was a significant association between mortality and the presence of shock (83%), ARDS

(87.5% in severe ARDS) and MODS (90-100% if MODS score ≥ 4) in this study which is corroborated in other studies. Heye et al [9] reported a 76.9% mortality rate associated with MODS whereas Pujari CG et al [23] reported a 58% mortality rate in severe ARDS. Jagrwal et al [24] reported a 32% mortality in patients with shock admitted in PICU, which is lower than in our study but they included patients not requiring mechanical ventilation as well.

Conclusion:

Mechanical ventilation is pivotal in the management of critically ill children admitted in pediatric ICUs and its proper utilisation is lifesaving. The various factors associated with adverse outcomes must be kept in mind and be dealt with in a timely manner. Prevention of complications and their timely management is key in achieving ideal outcomes for children requiring ventilation. This study and many others can help formulate and promulgate standard practices in various ICU settings for the betterment of healthcare.

Limitations: Smaller sample size was the limitation of our study. The findings of this study can be further strengthened with a larger sample size and multicentric studies and can also help in development of proper mechanical ventilation protocols in tertiary centres such as ours that are located and cater to multiple districts and demographics of patients.

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